

**PEDAGOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR A MODERN MUSIC TEACHER AND HIS
POSSIBILITIES OF USING TECHNOLOGIES**

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Annotation: Pedagogical skill of a music teacher is to organize all forms of the educational process in the most convenient and effective way, to direct them towards the goals of personal development, to form the ability of musical and spiritual worldview in students, necessary for society. It is considered one of the main tasks to arouse a tendency to activity. This article also addresses the same issues.

Key words: piano, technology, music, pedagogical expertise.

Based on the analysis of national experience and world-class achievements in the educational system, high general and professional culture, creative and social activity, able to independently set goals in social and political life, promote and solve future tasks the skills of pedagogues play a special role in the formation of a new generation of personnel.

As envisaged in the national program, modern information technologies and computers are perfected and applied to all educational processes, including the process of teaching music. Pedagogical skill of a music teacher is to organize all forms of the educational process in the most convenient and effective way, to direct them towards the goals of personal development, to form the ability of musical and spiritual worldview in students, to the activities necessary for society. Arousal of inclination is considered one of the main tasks.

It is known that the purpose of musical-pedagogical activity is determined by society, that is, the result of musical-pedagogical activity is related to the interests of society. The work of a music teacher is aimed at the development of the personality of young people in all aspects. Accordingly, musical-pedagogical activity ensures the social unity (sequence) of the generation. It transfers the musical experience of one generation to the next generation, realizes the natural possibilities of musical understanding in a person to gain social experience.

A music teacher works with young people who are constantly growing. It is impossible to use the same pattern and established behavior in approaching them in terms of musical education. This requires the music teacher to constantly search creatively.

The most urgent issue and task today is to implement the standards of music education in the educational process. If this task is not carried out, the issues of achieving quality and efficiency in the field of musical education and training, improving the educational process will remain unresolved.

First of all, the teacher of music culture should study the experiences gained in the field of education and training. This will surely help in solving many problems. In addition to the activities of experienced music teachers, the activities of ordinary teachers are also studied. Because in the study of experiences in music education, problems, achievements and shortcomings in the process are identified. The methods of observation, interviews, questionnaires, question-and-answer, study of students' written and creative works, pedagogical documents are used. For example: a pedagogical phenomenon that needs to be studied in observation is recorded based on the results of

observation based on a certain goal. This process should be carried out on the basis of a clear plan. The interview is conducted in order to collect various evidence or clarify the musical materials collected during the observation. "Conversation is used as an independent or auxiliary method." Questionnaire is carried out in order to collect material related to music. A skilled music teacher should study the musical documents of all students. This includes the participation of students in extracurricular musical activities, documents of education in a music school. He also conducts extracurricular activities in the music club. For example: In ancient Greece, it was believed that wisdom and courage can be cultivated with the help of music.

In fact, every art has a spiritual effect on a person. Music, in particular, has great power in emotional impact. Therefore, music is widely used in many directions in many countries.

A music teacher conducts educational and educational work. He should not only have wide knowledge, but also know his science well and deeply. Worldview, thinking, and understanding are of primary importance in educating children with the art of music. Music actively develops a person's feelings, especially emotional and aesthetic feelings. Musiqa o'qituvchisi yaxshi sozanda va yaxshi san'atkor bo'lishi lozimdir. Musiqa cholg'usida yaxshi chalishi, ijro eta olishi, yaxshi ovozga ega bo'lishi, notaga qarab yaxshi ijro qilishi, bolalar qobiliyatini ajrata bilishi lozimdir.

In addition to these, the teacher should monitor the lessons of other subjects. He acquires his pedagogical skills through constant observations. He learns to assess the situation, to feel the inner feelings of students. Observation is carried out during grades 1-7. The most important thing: the teacher should not only play the piece of music, but also introduce its content, for this the teacher's speech should be fluent, short and understandable.

In the lesson of music culture, the teacher's skills should be at a high level in all aspects. Through his introduction to the piece and explanation of the lesson, he introduces students to the world of wonderful and magical music. And with an interesting conversation, children can focus on music topics. The teacher's story about the piece of music should be short, interesting and should bring students to artistic perception. If the teacher uses the method of communication with the students during the lesson, it will help them to think correctly about music and make clear conclusions. In the course of the conversation, more students will go to the debate. In this activity, the teacher should lead them like a director and reach the right conclusions.

Today, the interest and attention to increase the effectiveness of music education using interactive methods in the educational process is growing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that, until now, in traditional education, the student was taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, but modern technologies allow them to independently find the acquired knowledge, study and analyze it independently, even teaches them to make their own conclusions.

In the opinion of teachers, researchers, and practitioners studying the issues and problems of music-pedagogical technology, music-pedagogical technology is defined as the use of various technical tools that must be used only in the teaching process.

In order to prepare students for innovative activities and to form related skills and qualifications, first of all, it is necessary to be able to effectively use educational and cognitive activities, to achieve that students acquire the skills of using pedagogical technologies in the teaching of each subject. For example, during conducting training, "Student training", "I am a conductor", "Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Scarabey", "Discussion", "Communication", "Group lib performance", "Small group holiday performance", "Individual performance", "Question - answer",

"Continue the tune", "Lesson trip", "Competition" in the teaching of the instrument performance class "lessons" technologies can be used and students can be prepared for such activities.

In short, music as art is a form of social consciousness. In addition to expressing one's feelings, it is a reflection of the reality of life and the times. The following are the main factors of the music lesson process: enjoying listening to music, playing songs, understanding the characteristics of music literacy, dancing and performing various movements to the sounds of music, clapping and playing musical instruments, understanding the purpose.

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